

HIGHER EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN THE PAN-AMAZON: THE CASE OF THE UFPA CENTER FOR ADVANCED AMAZONIAN STUDIES

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José Nilberlanio Vieira

PPGDSTU/NAEA/UFPA, Brazil. Email: nilber2004@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Higher education in the Amazon, including the highest levels of education such as *stricto sensu* postgraduate studies, represents an extremely important opportunity for the development of the region and its people, as it favors social mobility (WANDERLEY, 2003). It is understood that the training received by professionals in higher education has implications and reflections on their specific social and economic reality, on the demands for solutions and improvements, as well as on the possibilities that emerge from their training received in higher education with a view to acting to reduce social inequality (LUCENA; LEAL, 2020). In this sense, this work, whose results are still preliminary, given that this is an ongoing research, addresses the monitoring and analysis of the professional trajectories of graduates of the *stricto sensu* postgraduate studies carried out by the Núcleo de Altos Estudos Amazônicos and their contribution to sustainable development in the Amazon and Pan-Amazon, considering the aspect of interdisciplinarity in the academic training of these graduates (PPGDSTU, 2021); UFPA (2022). Its research locus is specifically the Postgraduate Program in Sustainable Development of the Humid Tropics (PPGDSTU), which constitutes the empirical analysis framework, considering that this is a subunit belonging to the Center for Advanced Amazonian Studies (NAEA), of the Federal University of Pará (UFPA) (PPGDSTU, 2021); (UFPA, 2022). **Keywords:** Higher education; *stricto sensu* postgraduate studies; monitoring of graduates; Center for Advanced Amazonian Studies (NAEA).

Methodology

This work uses a methodology that prioritizes the qualitative and exploratory character, aiming to explore the reflections of graduates about their training for sustainable development received in the course. Survey-type questionnaires were applied to master's and doctoral graduates, with the time frame from 2007 to 2020, obeying the ethical principles of scientific research (CRESWEL, 2007); (CHIZZOTTI, 2000); (LAKATOS; MARCONI, 2003); (MINAYO, 2004).

Stricto sensu postgraduate studies at UFPA

According to the most recent data, relating to the year 2022, available on the website of the Pro-Rector of Planning and Institutional Development (Proplan), UFPA currently has 144 stricto sensu postgraduate courses, 96 of which are master's courses and 48 doctoral courses, responsible for the training of 1,058 masters and 362 doctors (UFPA, 2022).

The impacts resulting from the training of these professionals are not limited to the academic sphere, extending significantly to society. This return can be interpreted through the production and dissemination of socially relevant knowledge, the promotion of technological innovation and the stimulus to regional inclusion (UFPA, 2022).

When analyzing these numbers in more detail, it becomes clear the important role played by UFPA in promoting advanced higher education and in qualifying highly qualified professionals. The significant number of postgraduate courses, both master's and doctoral, attests to the institution's commitment to research and scientific development, fostering the advancement of knowledge in various areas of knowledge. This understanding is corroborated by Costa (1998, p. 100) when he points out that:

“(…) UFPA is today a complex institution, whose main characteristic is to have institutional mechanisms that allow it to simultaneously house multiple disciplines in both natural and social sciences and the S&T subfields of teaching and research”.

In this context, the training of masters and doctors contributes to enriching the academic environment, but also substantially to society in general. The production of socially relevant knowledge drives progress, while the technological innovation resulting from these programs can have positive impacts on the economy and regional competitiveness.

Furthermore, the promotion of a meaningful education such as that provided by UFPA's stricto sensu postgraduate program requires the effective integration of several fundamental principles. In this context, critical thinking emerges as an essential tool, enabling individuals to question, analyze, and interpret information autonomously. By fostering this skill, the educational institution aims to create an intellectually enriching environment, where students are encouraged to develop independent perspectives and face complex challenges.

Integrated learning emerges as a complement, seeking to transcend traditional disciplinary barriers. This approach provides a more complete and contextualized understanding of knowledge, preparing students to face problems that require an

interdisciplinary view. The interconnection between different areas of knowledge, in addition to enriching learning, stimulates creativity and innovative resolution of contemporary issues.

However, the effectiveness of this educational process is not limited to cognitive development. The integration of values such as citizen engagement and respect for diversity broadens the social impact of education. Citizen engagement encourages students to become active agents in society, aware of their role in social, political and community issues. The aim is to develop ethical citizens, committed to the common good and capable of contributing to a more just and participatory society.

The appreciation of Amazonian culture fits into this context as a fundamental component of respect for the people and their ways of life. Recognizing and preserving the cultural riches of the Amazon region enriches students' cultural repertoire and promotes a deeper and more respectful understanding of cultural diversity. By integrating Amazonian cultural elements into the educational process, the institution contributes to the construction of strong and sustainable identities, valuing the existing cultural plurality.

In addition to these aspects, UFPA, by contributing with its *stricto sensu* postgraduate courses to the educational process, fosters critical thinking, integrated learning, citizen engagement, appreciation of Amazonian culture and respect for diversity, creating an environment conducive to the integral development of students, with a positive impact when these students graduate and begin to contribute their knowledge to the society in which they live. This synergy between different aspects prepares individuals to be conscious, innovative and culturally sensitive citizens, capable of contributing positively to the society in which they live.

It can be inferred, therefore, that graduates of *stricto sensu* postgraduate courses, in particular, reinforce the strategic importance of UFPA as a driving force behind educational, scientific and technological development, highlighting its fundamental role in building a more robust and innovative future for the region and the country, with NAEA and PPGDSTU included in this transformative process, as can be seen from Costa (1998).

Stricto sensu postgraduate studies and monitoring of graduates

Monitoring graduates is an important activity and must be linked to the mission and final objectives of the institution, or, more specifically, of the *stricto sensu* postgraduate program, whose main commitment is to improve the training offered to graduates, considering the quality of teaching, the expansion of research and their effective involvement with society,

aiming at improving the quality of life, that is, the contribution of this graduate to social development and not just to know the professional destiny of the graduate per se, since their actions can lead to a social, environmental, economic, political, cultural impact, etc.

For Hortale et al. (2014), there is still a lack of data when it comes to graduates of postgraduate programs and, in this context, monitoring would allow a more detailed analysis of the effects of training on the professional trajectory, in addition to providing support for possible adjustments in the training and curricular processes (CAETANO SILVA; PATTA BARDAGI, 2016), as well as enabling the expansion of knowledge of academic management bodies about the training processes, establishing a line of action for monitoring the trajectory of graduates and supporting the improvement of the monitoring processes of graduates of stricto sensu postgraduate programs.

Andriola (2006) states that it is highly relevant to investigate the social repercussions of the activities of a HEI, for example, through the systematic monitoring of its graduates. In this specific case, the monitoring of graduates of stricto sensu postgraduate courses is taken as an important mechanism to map opinions, attitudes and beliefs about the university, the course that the graduate completed, as well as the graduate's contribution to society, identifying and evaluating the value added by the HEI, regarding the adequacy and relevance of the professional and civic training of the human resources trained.

Furthermore, observing the trajectory of graduates can serve as a source of management information, allowing decision-making on planning actions to improve the course offered by the PPG to future students. It is also important that the PPG maintains contact with former students, because according to Leopoldo (2019, p. 39):

When this link is not maintained, there is a distance between the educational institution and the graduate student. To avoid this, the institution needs to create a solid database that is capable of providing support for the development of future actions aimed at the growth of the course and benefiting future students.

In this context, it is important to establish a communication channel with graduates in order to hear their perceptions, criticisms, compliments and suggestions for improving the course. Nowadays, this can be done online, with the help of information and communication technologies, providing a permanent link with the graduate.

It is worth noting that the PPGDSTU/NAEA is a postgraduate course in the interdisciplinary area with a score of 6 in the CAPES evaluation (2013 to 2016) and a score of 7 in the evaluation for the four-year period 2017 to 2020. Since its creation, it has sought to

offer solid training to graduates, contributing to research, teaching and extension at the university, also aiming at social mobility and the impact of the training of its graduates on society. Its objectives include training researchers, teachers and professionals who think about economic and regional development in the Amazon, together with the principles of conservation and environmental preservation with the generation of social prosperity.

In addition to this objective, it also advocates for carrying out research and reflections at an international level, connected with the current debates of its time about the development of the Humid Tropics in Pan-Amazonian countries, always attentive to the challenges posed by the socio-environmental complexity that permeates the Amazonian reality.

In the period covered by this research (2007 to 2020), whose time frame is justified by covering four evaluations with Capes, two triennial (2007 to 2009 and 2010 to 2012) and two quadrennial (2013 to 2016 and 2017 to 2020), since the evaluation frequency was changed by Capes from 2013 onwards (ceasing to be triennial and becoming quadrennial), the PPGDSTU trained 170 master's students and 190 doctoral students.

Regarding the country of origin, table 01 below summarizes the total number of master's and doctoral students graduated during the period:

Master's degree		PhD	
Country of origin	Amount	Country of origin	Amount
Brazil	162	Brazil	181
Colombia	03	Colombia	02
Ecuador	02	Ecuador	01
Peru	02	Peru	01
Japan	01	Venezuela	01
-	-	Guiana	01
-	-	Guinea Bissau	01
-	-	Netherlands	01
-	-	Japan	01
Total	170	-	190

Source: Prepared by the author, based on data from the PPGDSTU/NAEA/UFPA Secretariat (2023)

This highlights the scope of the Program in the Pan-Amazonian countries, which demonstrates the level of internationalization of the Program not only among the Pan-Amazonian countries, but also at a global level. In this sense, the PPGDSTU has sought to insert itself in the debates and innovative experiences in engaged field research of an interdisciplinary nature, carried out by a highly qualified faculty with national and international experience.

It is important to mention the scope of his research, which is part of projects that investigate areas such as socio-environmental and regional development, management of

natural resources, indigenous and quilombola peoples and traditional peoples and communities, family farming, regional economy, rural and urban human settlements in Amazonian areas, socio-environmental conflicts, social dynamics in mining areas in the Pan-Amazon, land use and land use change, migrations and population dynamics in the Pan-Amazon, etc.

This experience is beneficial for students and graduates, as it provides a rich and diverse education, contributing to the graduate's social mobility and helping them to enter different activities in the world of work and society.

Results and discussion

Preliminary results indicate that graduates of the Master's and Doctorate programs of the Postgraduate Program in Sustainable Development of the Humid Tropics (PPGDSTU/NAEA) have a variety of academic backgrounds, highlighting the interdisciplinary nature of the program. Furthermore, the fact that students are attracted from various regions of Brazil and even from Pan-Amazonian countries highlights the program's reputation in the area of socio-environmental studies. The motivation for choosing the PPGDSTU/NAEA for the Master's program involves factors such as the prestige of the institution, the grade awarded by Capes and the lack of other similar options at the time of their studies. The interdisciplinarity of the program and its focus on the sustainability of the Amazon were also considered relevant.

The emphasis on interdisciplinarity allowed graduates to build knowledge in areas such as political science, ecological economics, political ecology and geography. In addition, the research also enabled them to deal with social and economic dimensions of sustainability.

The high rate of master's degree graduates who chose to continue in the program by pursuing a doctorate suggests a level of satisfaction and recognition of the quality of the program by students. This indicates that the PPGDSTU/NAEA meets the needs for advanced training in topics related to sustainable development and socio-environmental issues.

In general, graduates of the Program emphasize that the knowledge acquired during their training in this program has a significant influence on their professional lives and contributes in several ways to society, such as: 1) development of research and writing skills; 2) Preparation for Teaching; 3) Expansion of Bibliographic and Authorial Knowledge; 4) Interdisciplinary Approach; 5) Access to High-Quality Research; 6) Professional Performance with Assertiveness, etc.

Graduates highlight several significant contributions of the program to their advanced postgraduate training, including: 1) Improvement of Knowledge; 2) Critical and Systemic Vision; 3) Expansion of Research Interests, among others.

The contribution of graduates to the sustainable development of the Amazon is quite significant. They work in a variety of areas, from academic research and student guidance to the development of public policies, extension projects and work with local communities. In addition, many of them have actively participated in development projects in Latin American and Pan-Amazonian countries, promoting an integrated and collaborative vision to address socio-environmental challenges.

However, some graduates note that they have not yet seen immediate economic results from the training, but believe that the value of the program's training will be more recognized in the future.

Regarding the monitoring of graduates, the research indicates that there is room for improvement. Although most graduates are familiar with the NAEA website, few are aware of the program's presence on digital networks, such as Instagram and Twitter, suggesting that the program should invest more in promoting these communication channels.

Regarding how graduates should be monitored, graduates suggest several ways, including invitations to academic events, participation in research groups, updating their Lattes CV, giving lectures and even promoting interaction events between graduates to share post-graduation experiences. The research also highlights that it is important for the program to maintain closer and more effective contact with graduates, involving them in academic activities and keeping them informed about opportunities for engagement.

These suggestions from graduates can be considered valuable for the continuous improvement of the PPGDSTU/NAEA, ensuring that it continues to contribute significantly to the expansion of the theoretical debate and practical experience in the daily lives of communities regarding the sustainable development of the Amazon and Pan-Amazon.

Conclusions/Final Considerations

It is clear that the Postgraduate Program in Sustainable Development of the Humid Tropics (PPGDSTU), of the Center for Advanced Amazonian Studies (NAEA) has played a fundamental role in the professional and academic training of its graduates. The testimonies of former students reflect the quality of teaching and knowledge acquired throughout the course,

as well as its contribution to the development of the Amazon and Pan-Amazonian Region in the context of sustainable development.

The PPGDSTU/NAEA stands out for its interdisciplinary approach and its focus on the Amazon, providing graduates with a deep understanding of the complexities of this unique region. They reported developing critical thinking, systemic vision and advanced research skills, as well as an appreciation for interpersonal relationships and the diversity of students' backgrounds.

Recommendations from graduates for improving the program include greater promotion of academic-scientific events, a platform for monitoring graduates, constant updating of content and disciplines, greater focus on political economy and the promotion of researcher networks.

Thus, for the alumni surveyed, the PPGDSTU/NAEA has proven to be an institution of excellence that prepares its graduates to make significant contributions to the sustainable development of the Amazon and the Pan-Amazon. Through solid interdisciplinary training and the active engagement of its alumni, the program plays a crucial role in building a more sustainable future for this vital region. Their contributions and recommendations show that the PPGDSTU/NAEA continues to be a reference in promoting knowledge and action in favor of sustainable development in the Amazon.

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